

CDC ROUND UP

JANUARY TO MARCH 2025

New Project Announcement: A Liverpool Digital Commons

The CDC is excited to collaborate with the University of Liverpool's Virtual Engineering Centre (VEC) to develop a digital commons - a shared digital resource designed to house and share valuable datasets focused on healthcare and local authority data. This initiative is governed through commons principles which have been developed through discussions with members of the local community through projects such as Round 'Ere and a Resident's Assembly.

By working together, we aim to create a sustainable and trusted resource that enables researchers, policy makers, and local organisations to make data-driven decisions that benefit public health and community services. Our team is committed to engaging with local communities, healthcare professionals, and policy makers to ensure that the commons is developed in a way that meets real-world need and aligns with ethical best practices. More information will be available as the team develop the commons.

Greater Data Kick-off

On 11th February we launched the Greater Data programme with our collaborators from Capacity and Cheshire and Merseyside Change and Integration team with a workshop focused on unlocking the potential of expert practitioners in children's workforce.

We had a variety of representatives from local councils within the Liverpool City Region (as well as Warrington and Cheshire West) who specialise in , Speakers at the event included Rob Tabb from Liverpool City Region Combined Authority, Adam Drage & Anika from Mersey Care NHS Foundation Trust, Cheshire and Merseyside Mental Health Programme and the CDC's own Gary Leeming, Emma Lo and Ellie Fielding.

For more information on the event and what's next for the project please check out Capacity's blog post on their reflections. <https://thisiscapacity.co.uk/data-innovation-in-action/>

DATA AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY EVENTS

Our First Community Data Hackathon

The Civic Data Cooperative proudly hosted its first Community Data Hackathon on 6th December 2024 at the Municipal Hotel in Liverpool City Centre. This was an inspiring event that brought together talented and enthusiastic participants from across the Liverpool City Region to explore innovative ways of leveraging data for community-driven solutions.

The hackathon was an open-invite event held, promoted via Eventbrite and this attracted a diverse group of people who shared a passion for data and a desire to network, collaborate and create. Attendees ranged from academics, students and those working within tech and data industries in the Liverpool City Region. The hackathon focused on the theme Community Through Data, inviting participants to explore how existing datasets could be made more accessible, insightful and impactful.

To set the scene, we started the event with a panel discussion about the Round 'Ere project undertaken in Widnes, with input from the CDC team, our collaborators at Capacity, and one of the RE Community Researchers.

The day culminated in a range of exciting solutions and initiatives including:

- A centralised web application that integrates datasets focussing on wellbeing
- Analysis of cycling and walking data in LCR and correlations with deprivation to highlight need for initiatives to encourage regular activity
- Insight inspired by the Round 'Ere project in Widnes to create a tool for better access to important services for residents.

The CDC is excited to utilise the insights and feedback from this hackathon to shape and tailor another hackathon event, scheduled to take place in Spring/Summer 2025.

Student Enterprise Public Health Challenge

The University of Liverpool's Careers and Employability team, in collaboration with the CDC, delivered the annual LCR Live Well Challenge. Now in its third year, the CDC has continued to support this initiative, inviting students from first-year undergraduate to postgraduate level to address public health challenges in the Liverpool City Region through innovative solutions. In 2025, the challenge launched with an engaging event attended by over 100 students. Programme Coordinator Lib Golding expressed excitement at the high level of engagement, noting the collaboration and idea-sharing among participants as they tackled real-world public health issues.

Over six weeks, students worked in teams as part of this extracurricular programme. They gained valuable insights from public health and local industry experts, applied professional tools and frameworks, and received support from the University's Careers & Employability team and employer partners. This year's theme focused on sustainability in healthcare, with teams developing 5-minute video presentations exploring challenges and proposing practical, sustainable solutions. As part of their final submissions, teams also created digital infographics. The top three ideas were selected to pitch their proposals to a panel of experts at a celebration event, where prizes were awarded to the winning team. All participants were invited to attend, with their infographics displayed around the venue to showcase the breadth of student contributions in what was a vibrant and inclusive finale.

The LCR Live Well Challenge demonstrates the University of Liverpool's ongoing commitment to interdisciplinary collaboration, public health innovation, and the development of student entrepreneurship. Since 2022, the CDC has partnered with the University to deliver this programme, offering extracurricular opportunities that inspire students to tackle real regional issues while building valuable employability skills. Reflecting on the challenge, organisers celebrated the students' creativity, hard work, and meaningful impact. The CDC also welcomed the opportunity to help foster new connections between students and local organisations, supporting the next generation of talent in making a difference in the region they study in.

PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

Update on the Liverpool City Region Residents' Assembly on Data and AI Innovation

In March 2025 the CDC hosted the LCR Residents' Assembly on Data and AI Innovation. The NHS Cheshire and Merseyside Data into Action programme, the Liverpool City Region Combined Authority, and the University of Liverpool's Civic Health Innovation Labs jointly convened this Assembly. Our question posed to residents was: "What does trustworthy and beneficial data and AI innovation look like for the Liverpool City Region?"

The first two days of the assembly focused on learning about Data and AI with presentations from Iain Buchan (CHIL), Rob Tabb (LCR CA), Jim Hughes and Andrea Astbury (NHS Data into Action) and Sam Ball (University of Liverpool). Their presentations helped residents understand how data and AI are being used across partner organisations. Rachel Coldicutt from Careful Trouble led the second day of the assembly by delving deeper into 'What is AI' and exploring the complexities of AI trade-offs.

Residents reconvened the following week to brainstorm, deliberate, and design what they want to see in an LCR Charter on Data & AI Innovation. On the final day of the assembly residents voted for which principles they would like to see in the Charter. We will use their recommendations to ratify a Liverpool City Region Data and Innovation Charter, one of the first of its kind in the world. This will give innovators and researchers in the region an actionable social license for data and AI innovation.

What next?

We plan to Launch the Charter in June 2025 where we will invite existing stakeholders of the LCR Civic Data Cooperative and Civic Health Innovation Labs, led by the LCR Combined Authority, to sign on to the principles of the charter. A dedicated how-to guide and microsite is being created. We will create a professional working group and host learning sessions for health, care and tech workers to learn about the charter. To find out more about the LCR Residents' Assembly on Data and AI Innovation please check out the [webpage](#).

Community of Practice on Participatory and Inclusive Data Stewardship Wraps Up with Brixham Event in March

Last month the CDC ran their final of four Participatory and Inclusive Data Stewardship Community of Practice workshops. This event was hosted in Brixham and jointly convened by the [Brixham Data Trust](#). These workshops have been designed to reflect on and discuss participatory methods and shared practice for inclusive data stewardship. In Brixham, attendees focused on doing data (stewardship) in place, the value of place-based participatory methods, and the challenges. Learn more on our: [Notion page](#)

TRAVEL

Gary Leeming visits Vietnam to Strengthen Healthcare Partnerships

CDC Director Gary and Principal Investigator Professor Iain Buchan visited Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, as part of an initiative to strengthen healthcare partnerships between the UK and Vietnam. This project, funded by the Department of Business and Trade's Non-ODA Economic Partnerships Fund, aimed to enhance the UK's expertise in health innovation while helping HCMC improve its healthcare capabilities.

The primary goal was to develop a strong UK-to-HCMC healthcare knowledge pipeline, supporting health innovation and strengthening the city's ability to implement new healthcare solutions. Another key focus was to establish a City2City partnership between HCMC and Liverpool City Region (LCR) to create lasting commercial healthcare collaborations.

During the visit, Director Gary met with representatives from the British Consulate in HCMC, CHIL, LCR, and Healthcare UK to discuss various topics, including healthcare cooperation, big data integration, training programs, research collaborations, and public involvement in AI and data-driven healthcare initiatives.

One of the highlights was a case study from Cheshire & Merseyside on how big data could be used to improve healthcare services, offering a roadmap for HCMC's own Big Data Centre for Healthcare. There were also discussions on technical training support, workforce development, and exchange programs to encourage collaboration between universities, public services, and private companies.

The aim of the visit was to build a sustainable, impactful healthcare partnership that benefits both regions by leveraging innovation, research, and public trust in new technologies. Stay tuned for updates on how this collaboration unfolds and its potential impact on global healthcare innovation.

Conferences

As the 2025 conference season begins the team have been busy attending various national conferences for networking and knowledge exchange.

- Rachael Wright attended 'Digital Health Rewired' in Birmingham, a UK digital health conference. She attended sessions focused on PPIE and how digital transformation can be used to benefit the NHS. Asra Aslam was also in attendance, presenting work on the DynAIRx study.
- Rachael Thompson and Claire Smith attended HETT North which was hosted in Manchester in February of this year. The conference provides a good opportunity to stay up to date with the latest technology trends and networking with partners in Industry and other organisations.
- Gary Leeming has had a paper accepted at MedInfo and will be in Taiwan in August to present.

Meet the Team: Ellie Fielding

Born in London but moved to Devon when she was 5, Ellie studied Archaeology and Anthropology at the University of Cambridge, where she played cricket helping to defeat Oxford's cricket team three years in a row and started rowing—. During an internship with *Time Team*, she unearthed Anglo-Saxon treasure and shared mead with Tony Robinson (her main task was finding the mead!).

After university, Ellie started her career at Imperial College London through a graduate training scheme, gaining experience across campus services, the Faculty of Engineering, the Education Directorate, and the Office of Financial Strategy.

Ellie went onto secure a job as an Investment Manager in the Office of Financial Strategy and managed property assets on behalf of Imperial College, including Georgian town houses in central London, a manor house in Ascot and 9 acres of expansion space in West London for a new commercial and translation campus.

When her wife took a job at Unilever, Ellie relocated to Liverpool, where she joined the Combined Authority's investment team delivering economic regeneration including land & property deals and innovation projects.

Seeing the challenges faced by residents in the city region, she became increasingly interested in public health and participatory methods, leading her to join the CDC as its fourth employee in August 2021. She played a key role in setting up the What's Your Problem? initiative and CDC operations, overseeing recruitment, finance, and reporting. Ellie also helped secure the CDC's first home at the Digital Innovation Facility and worked with the MIRC team to design and deliver the CHIL offices.

After taking maternity leave nine months ago to welcome baby Miles, she's now back for the final 12 months of the CDC. As keen runner, Ellie is using the office commute to sneak in buggy free runs and is enjoying drinking hot tea again!

What's coming up?

As the CDC enters its final year there are lots of exciting projects still being undertaken. In the next newsletter there will be further information on the launch of our Podcast and Digital Commons.

The CDC are also working with the **Digital Commons Policy Council to host a hybrid 2-day event in May 2025**, welcoming in-person delegates to Liverpool. In June there will be the Launch of the LCR Charter on Data & AI Innovation and the Hackathon.

If any of these projects are of interest to you, we would be more than happy to share more information or look at ways in which you can get involved. Please see our contact details below.

Contact Us

If you have questions, please get in touch with our team who will be able to assist you.

Email: cdc.info@liverpool.ac.uk

Bluesky: [@civicdatacoop](https://bsky.app/profile/civicdatacoop). [bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/bsky.social)

LinkedIn: [LCR Civic Data Cooperative](#) | [LinkedIn](#)

Gary also contributed to the below evidence piece responding to the Science, Innovation and Technology Committee inquiry into how research and innovation can boost regional economic growth and help to deliver the Government's Missions on 'Mobilising UK Data and AI for All with a National Grid of Civic Learning Systems' committees.parliament.uk/writtenevidence/135499/pdf/

As part of the Community of Practice, Dr Emily Rempel has been involved in reviewing publications on the 'Choral Data 'Trust' Experiment White Paper' and on 'Participatory and inclusive data stewardship: A landscape review.'